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Review Article

A Review On 3d Printing Technologies for Drug Delivery in Pharmaceuticals

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ABSTRACT

The application of In the field of pharmaceuticals, the use of 3D printers has been grown dramatically in current time due to its many benefits over conventional pharmaceutical manufacturing methods. In this new world, 3D printing has already demonstrated its promise by demonstrating impressive uses the development of pharmaceutical delivery systems. The formulation of their own floating medicine delivery device using various 3D printing methods and materials. The purpose of 3D printing the objective is to develop delivery systems customized for each individual person's need. Pharmaceutical and Clinical pharmaceutical products including tablets, are essential components of modern medicine, capslets, film, combination medications, microdoses, eco-friendly patches, healthcare devices, personalized implants. prosthetics/anatomical structures, surgical models, etc. made with 3D printing are among the various aspects of 3D printing innovation that are being presented. Healthcare additive manufacturing is still in its infancy. Although still under development, it has already found diverse applications within the medical sector .which is already under tremendous pressure to perform at its best and cut expenses . This review explores the applications of 3D printing in the medical field, highlighting the advantages, challenges, and overall potential of the technology.

INTRODUCTION

The idea of "personalized medicine" has garnered a lot of interest lately as a way to tailor therapy to each patient's requirements. The potential for personalized care for every patient is made

possible by technological advancements! The effectiveness of individualized therapy is influenced Several factors contribute to this, including, individual biological difference, differences in living and working environments,

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interactions between drugs and herbs and foods, and various illnesses. Therefore, it's critical to develop a universal process. To create compositions it, according to specific needs, may distribute drugs without the right characteristics. Three-dimensional printing technology has the capability to precisely manage the space and dispense small amounts of medication for personalized drug administration. 3D printing technology has been thoroughly studied. The landscape of drug delivery has evolved significantly since the FDA approved the first levetiracetam 3D-printed tablet, known as Spritam^[1,2]. 3D printing is a method that constructs a three-dimensional object incrementally from a digital design. This innovative technique, initially introduced for rapid prototyping in the early 1990s, involves the sequential deposition of multiple layers to create solid forms. Originating over three decades ago from advancements in chemistry, optics, and robotics, this method was originally employed to produce models using UV-cured resin^[3,4]. In its simplest form, a 3-D printer uses computer-aided design and programming to create three-dimensional objects by layering substance onto a basis. Initially, To create the component's a basis, the material is extruded onto the x and y planes from the printer's head. Subsequently, a liquid binder is applied to this base as the printer moves along the z-axis, building up to the required thickness. Although the process is executed repeatedly following the computer's directives, Layer after layer, the item is built gradually. Following a treatment procedure that gets rid of any unbound molecules, the finished product is finished. Pharmaceutical dose forms that are highly reproducible and carefully regulated may be produced using this 3D printing technique. Software for electronic design is used to create. Objects of any dimensions. However, this might be mistaken with additive processes like film lamination, coating, and capsule filling in

pharmaceutical manufacture. Biomedical, pharmaceutical, construction, architecture, and aerospace are just several current and emerging industries are heavily utilizing 3D printing technology. The manufacturing sector has been using it for decades. Small-scale production processes like prototyping, customization, producing complicated items, and democratizing ideas that are frequently challenging to build using conventional techniques can all benefit from this. In addition, it reduces energy and material waste, speeds up time to market, promotes environmental sustainability, and eventually lowers production costs. Scientists are now eager to transform the pharmaceutical and healthcare sectors by using 3DP technology to the large-scale manufacturing of medicinal dosage forms.^[5] 3D printing is increasingly utilized across various industries, with its applications continually expanding. The concept of 3D printing was first introduced in the 1970s, utilizing a high-energy beam to construct objects layer by layer by solidifying powdered materials. This method is referred to as "selective laser sintering." Subsequently, during the 1980s and 1990s, new printing techniques such as fused deposition modeling (FDM) and stereolithography (SLA) emerged. Initially, the automotive and aerospace industries adopted 3D printing to enhance the prototyping process. Over time, its applications have broadened to encompass fields such as jewelry, art, education, and construction^[6,7]. Because of its ability to create tailored medication that can achieve the best possible therapeutic results with the fewest possible adverse effects, 3D printing is becoming more and more popular in pharmaceutical and medical research and application. In addition to customized medicine dosage forms, many advanced drug delivery systems, including prolonged drug release, fixed dose combination, and gastro-retentive platforms, have been created utilizing various 3D printing methods^[8,9]. A variety of

innovative floating medicine delivery system designs created using 3D printing have been created and released in recent years^[10,11]. The challenges associated with traditional methods of preparing floating drug delivery systems, such as tableting and coating—particularly the difficulty in adjusting doses due to the inability to break tablets—can be effectively resolved through this printing technique. Additionally, because each patient has a varied stomach emptying interval, the medication is delivered at various body locations in each patient. Therefore, customized dosage forms and preparation are required for floating medication delivery systems. This review explains

how to build a gastro-retentive medication delivery system using 3D printing technology. The preparation methods for floating medication delivery systems—both conventional and innovative—are examined and updated. The benefits and areas for development of the floating medication delivery devices made using 3D printing are examined and addressed. Lastly, the writers' thoughts regarding the viability and future of 3D printing are explored.^[12]

Over the last fifteen years, the pharmaceutical business has used a number of various methods of 3D printing.

Figure1: Classification of different 3D printing techniques.

Types Of Printers in The Pharmaceutical Field:

Pharmaceutical dosage forms are manufactured using a variety of techniques for 3D printing. Four of the most widely used methods of three-dimensional printing are light introduction polymerization, liquid dispersion on powder, FDM 3D thermal inkjet (TIJ), and several more have been created.

1. Fused deposition modelling:

The procedure comprises selecting the suitable thermoplastic polymer, melting it, and then extruding it via a movable, heated nozzle. The molten polymer is added layer by layer. It then

takes on the desired shape that was created using computer-aided design models. This approach may be applied to dosage forms that incorporate polymers, such as implants and constant-drug-release tablets. There are several advantages to FDM 3D printing. FDM printers, for example, are fairly priced, and the materials they use are widely available and economically priced. Furthermore, printing precision alone may be used to swiftly make high-detail goods. Because of their limitations in terms of feature complexity, FDM printers work best with finer models or professional-quality prototypes can generate^[13].

Figure:2 Fused deposition modelling

2. 3D Thermal ink jet:

This technique generates a vapour bubble by heating the ink fluid using a micro-resistor, which forces the ink to drop out of the nozzle. Pneumatic extrusion and drop-on-demand inkjet printing are the terms for these processes. The 3D TIJ differs

from other printers in that it can print liquid with a range of properties. Medical preparations and solutions have been distributed spontaneously using this technique. It can also be used in the production of medicinal goods [14].

Figure:3 Thermal Ink Jet

3. Liquid dispensing on powdered form:

This powder-based 3D printing technique involves spraying or dropping different mixes of ink and active chemicals in varying droplet sizes onto a powder substrate, which then solidifies into a solid dose form. This technique's benefit is its capacity

for large-scale expansion. Additionally, the substance is porous and low in density, which makes it perfect for creating dosage forms for tablets that dissolve quickly. An example of a final product with a smooth exterior is Zip Dose. For this reason, grinding is usually not required [15].

Figure :4 Liquid dispensing on powder form

4. Light-induced polymerization:

Light-induced polymerization is a three-dimensional printing technique that solidifies light-sensitive polymers or radiation-curable resins one layer at a time using light or ultraviolet (UV) radiation. It has developed into a number of sophisticated 3D printing methods, including as SLA, digital light processing, and continuous direct light processing, and is currently used to create prototypes or product Molds. Detailed and complex designs can be produced with light-

induced polymeric reaction printers; the surface of the finished product is smooth, often eliminating the need for grinding; light-induced polymerization models are made with resin, which can be damaged by extending exposition to sunlight; furthermore, printing duration and expenditures are higher than satisfactory; Technical know-how is necessary to operate three-dimensional printers since light-induced polymerization is complex and inappropriate for inexperienced users ^[16].

Figure 5: Light induced polymerization

5 Stereolithography (SLA) Printer:

Stereolithography creates three-dimensional structures by using a computer-controlled laser beam to solidify liquid polymers or resin.³⁰ Compared to earlier forms of other 3DP,

stereolithography offers a number of benefits, chief among them being its remarkable resolution and avoidance of heat procedures that may be hazardous to certain drug compounds ^[15].

Figure 6: Stereolithography(SLA) Printer

History In Development Of 3d Technology of Healthcare:

Charles Hull is regarded as the father of 3D printing as he created, developed, and offered for sale the first 3D printing equipment in the middle of the 1980s. The STL file format works with current CAD programs. Stereolithography (SL), a technique developed by Hull, involves using a laser to cure a liquid resin surface. The stage then undergoes another immersion to allow for the cure of a subsequent layer. Layer by layer, this process is done until the desired shape is reached. The University of Texas at Austin (UT Austin), The company, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), and other businesses creating innovative additive manufacturing technology were all working on projects concurrently Hull submitted his patent application for his stereolithography, or apparatus (SLA) in the same year that a UT Austin researcher and his advisor submitted a selective laser melting (SLS) patent application. By fusing or sintering a powder bed with a laser beam, decreasing the powder bed, and then applying fresh powder, SLS produces three-dimensional

objects. By employing a normal inkjet print head to deposit "ink" or an adhesive solution into a powdered bed, MIT professors created the term "3Dprinter" to refer to a stacking process that binds powder. The process is then repeated layer by layer to obtain the desired shape. The free or nonbonded material that supported [University of Liverpool]'s processing on December 5, 2015, at 23:29. This procedure is commonly referred to as 3D printing. Scott Crump, a co-founder of Stratasys, Ltd., filed a patent application in 1989 on fused deposition modelling (FDM). In this study, we'll call this method 3D powder bed or powder bed inkjet printing. In this process, layers of hardened material are deposited until the required form is achieved. Materials including molten metals, thermoplastic resins, and self-hardening waxes can be employed in this process. Scientists at Helisys, now known as Cubic Technologies, invented the laminated object manufacturing (LOM) process in 1996. Certain materials are piled in sheets that have been formed (typically with lasers) and joined by welding or adhesives [25].

Table1: History And Evolution of Healthcare 3d Technologies

Year	Events
1984	Chuck Hull invents Stereolithography (SLA), the first 3D printing technology.
1987	3D Systems releases the first 3D printer, the SLA-11.
1990	Emerging 3D printing methods include Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) and Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM).
2000	Expiration of key patents leads to the democratization of 3D printing with low-cost, open-source printers like RepRap and Makerbot.
2010	Advances in 3D bioprinting and metal 3D printing, expanding applications in medical and industrial fields.
2020	Continued growth in precision, repeatability, and material range, making 3D printing viable for industrial production.

Pharmaceutical And Healthcare Uses Of 3D Printing:

Because of its benefits in boosting production efficiency, cutting costs, and removing human error, 3D printing technology is quickly expanding throughout industrial manufacturing industries. In addition to altering industrial output, 3D printing has also shifted the emphasis on industrial automation. This is due to its high degree of adaptability, customization capabilities, and capacity to produce a vast array of forms, ranging from basic to intricate. In order to produce high-quality pharmaceutical products with improved process resilience, the biomedical product development industry, which now relies on manufacturing medicines using traditional manufacturing techniques, is quickly adopting 3D printing. Furthermore, the biomedical engineering of medical devices for therapeutic and diagnostic uses has shown 3D printing to be beneficial. We present an updated evaluation of the previously suggested applications of 3D printing in early-phase drug development, building on earlier studies on medicinal manufacturing and biological applications of 3D printing. The active component needs to be formulated in a practical way so that clinical safety and effectiveness investigations may be carried out in the early stages of drug development" The physiochemical characteristics of the active ingredient must be carefully

examined in order to create a dosage form that can be utilized to assess the new medication's therapeutic advantages. Dosage forms may be created by 3D printing at an early stage of drug discovery with minimal time, effort, or financial investment. High dose flexibility and bioavailability features are also provided, which are necessary for formulations created for various patient groups in various geographic locations and to satisfy the requirements of various clinical sites. These features can be printed on dosage forms to support the rapid advancement of clinical trials within a limited time frame" Traditional manufacturing, which is very labour-intensive, costly due to larger batch sizes, and requires extensive preformulation studies to maximize efficiency and ramp up the formula in order to manufacture the requisite dosage forms, does not have these benefits. Specially designed medications The potential of 3D printing to create medications that are specific to patient populations can help individuals or groups receive individualized treatment plans ^[17,18]. Therefore, in addition to treating young and old patients, 3D printing can be a helpful therapeutic tool for treating complex condition including cancer, Alzheimer's disease, and epilepsy. Individualized therapy promises to provide patients the proper dosage at the right time to achieve the best possible drug therapy outcomes and show desired

pharmacokinetic (PK) and pharmacodynamic (PD) responses. Furthermore, while designing titration and formulations, these medicines take into account additional variables such as body weight, age, gender, and genetic composition. Conventional dose forms, on the other hand, sustain a significant section of the patient population by relying only on a set strength. Furthermore, whereas conventional treatment depends on the creation of a comprehensive production setup with top-tier equipment, 3D printing offers flexibility for on-site fabrication. Therefore, rather than taking a population-centric approach to treatment, 3D printing may encourage

an individual-centric one. Complex medication treatment Designing intricate dosage forms with several narrow therapeutic index drug dosages to facilitate long-acting medication therapy may be made easier using 3D printing. In order to sustain blood medication levels for the intended therapeutic impact over an extended period of time, patients frequently need to take many tablets for illness indications when using standard dose forms. Reduced patient compliance, missed doses that cause blood level changes, and high expenses are only a few of the disadvantages of this strategy [19,20].

Figure 7: Medical Healthcare Applications Of 3DPrinting.

Benefits Of 3D Printing:

According to reports, three-dimensional printing has a number of benefits over traditional production in the pharmaceutical industry. To start, 3D printing can increase output. In addition to being quicker than conventional techniques, 3D printing offers better resolution, repeatability, accuracy, and consistency when it comes to manufacturing pharmaceutical items like implants and prosthesis. Second, 3D printing may be utilized to make drug dose forms and other individualized and tailored items. Finally, the

three-dimensional generated products are reasonably priced. The use of 3D printers is beneficial for small-scale manufacturing enterprises or businesses that create complex items or parts utilized for preoperative planning and customized preoperative treatment because all of its elements are essentially inexpensive. This will result in a multi-step process that determines the optimal therapy approach by combining clinical and imaging data. Numerous studies have shown that individualized pretrial preparation can reduce operating room (OR) time and decrease

complications. Additionally, this might lead to cheaper medical costs, shorter reinterventions, and shorter surgical stays [21,22,23].

Personalize Surgical Devices And Tools:

Custom surgical tools, guides, and implants may be made via 3D printing. Consequently, cost reductions are achieved by customizing surgical tools and prostheses using the of additive manufacturing. osteoarthritis disorders. 3D printing aids in evaluating an individual's response to medicine. Better surgical therapy selection and a more accurate evaluation of the patient's bone health are made possible by this. Enhancing educational opportunities in medicine printed using 3D printer specific to patients' models have been shown to improve learners' productivity and facilitate rapid learning in the field while also boosting management skills, wisdom, and self-assurance. The ability to model various physiologic and pathologic anatomy from a large dataset of images, the reproducibility and safety of the 3D-printed model in comparison to cadaver breakdown, and the ability to distribute 3D models among institutions—especially those that have limited resources—are some of the benefits of 3D printing in education. To highlight the internal intricacies, 3D printers with a variety of print densities and colours might be utilized [24,25,26].

3D Printing Technologies In Drug Manufacturing:

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0) is characterized by the convergence of digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and 3D printing, leading to a paradigm shift in manufacturing processes. 3D printing, in particular, holds immense potential to revolutionize drug manufacturing by enabling the production of highly customized and complex drug delivery systems. [45].

Key Advantages Of 3d Printing In Drug Manufacturing:

- **Customized Health Care:** By enabling the development of customized medication delivery systems that address each patient's unique requirements, 3D printing enhances treatment effectiveness and lowers adverse effects.

- **Complicated Compositions:** The technique allows for the creation of novel and efficient therapies by producing complex drug formulations with exact control over dose and release patterns [27,28].

- **Quick Prototyping:** By facilitating the quick testing and prototyping of novel formulations and devices, 3D printing speeds up the drug development process.

- **Lower Costs:** 3D printing may lower production costs and increase efficiency by doing away with the requirement for conventional manufacturing Molds and equipment.

- **Better Supply Chain Management:** Using 3D printing to produce pharmaceuticals locally can assist to minimize supply chain interruptions and guarantee prompt access to prescription prescriptions

- **Drug Distribution Methods:** A variety of drug delivery systems, such as tablets, capsules, implants, and patches, with individualized characteristics like dose, release rate, and targeting, may be produced by 3D printing.

- **Organ-on-a-Chip Models:** Drug development and research can be expedited by using 3D printed organ-on-a-chip models to mimic how the human physique reacts to medications [29].

Examples Of 3d Printed Drugs-

- **Spritam (Levetiracetam):** The US Food and therapy Agency (FDA) authorized this seizure therapy in 2015, making it the first FDA-approved 3D printed pharmaceutical.

- **Rheumatoid Arthritis Drug:** A clinical trial employing a 3D printed medication for those with rheumatoid arthritis patients was authorized by the FDA in February 2021.

Zip Dose: Aprelia Pharmaceuticals 3D printed tablet technology has been used to create personalized medications with varying release profiles

Oro dispersible Formulations: Researchers have used 3D printing to create rapidly dissolving orodispersible formulations for patients with swallowing difficulties.

Gastro-Retentive Tablets: 3D printing has been used to develop gastro-retentive tablets that can remain in the stomach for extended periods.

Minitablets: Small tablets with exact dosage and regulated distribution profiles are now possible thanks to 3D printing.

Polyprintlets: Researchers have developed flexible multi-drug combinations using 3D printing, allowing for personalized treatment regimens^[30]. These illustrations show how 3D printing technology might be used to create customized pharmaceuticals. with specific release profiles, shapes, and sizes, improving patient compliance and treatment outcomes. In future digital healthcare, individualized characteristics of drug delivery systems will be pretty much highlighted through modernizing already employed and established pharmaceutical production processes. The fundamental basis for implementing such scenarios is the development

of internal active feedback between the medicinal product and requirements of every patient^[31]. In this regard, the technology has already shown tremendous promise in delivering personalised drug products either based on the dosage of the medication or on the size and structure of the product. Even though the clinical translation and regulatory framework for 3D-printed pharmaceutical products are still in their infancy, many scenarios that include this incorporation in future healthcare settings have been put up in the literature. This is a review study that will focus mainly on the 3D printing of medication delivery systems. Account being taken of the technology's capacity for controlled release and for adjusting the dose, we provide a summary of the scenarios proposed. Common problems with setting up 3D printers across various sites of production, which include hospitals, community pharmacies, or patient homes. The discussion is the final one addressing scenarios related to current hospital drug shortages, the necessity of a sophisticated networking capability between various production locations, and the paramount importance of establishing a comprehensive regulatory framework. Special patient demographics and polypharmacy response will be considered^[32].

Figure 8: Braille symbols on 3D-printed oral films (left) and tablets (right) allow visually challenged patients to identify the dose form.

3D Printing in Transdermal Delivery Systems (TDS): systems shall give painless, and immediate pharmacological treatment to patients and doctors

and avoid the shortcomings of conventional delivery systems like fear of needles, pain or gastrointestinal issues. TDD will be a great

candidate for the future because 3D printing, a rapidly developed technology that benefited thousands of industries, is going to pave the way to customized, tailored delivery plans. The TDD may completely benefit from the reasoning underlying one on one manufacturing, that is the foundation of 3 Dimensional printing technology, in a number of ways. For the production of priming doses, gradually rising or dropping dosages, and other applications, systems with layers of different drug concentrations is able to be created & copied. layering with varying levels of drugs that alternate,

which may be formulated based on the pharmacological process, are also possible. can be modified to meet the requirements of kids, who are known to become irritated by conventional transdermal methods. Since each person has a different range of factors that affect the rate of drug absorption, including skin thickness, hydration levels, and sensitivity level, the flexibility of customization provided by It is believed that the TDD route is more successful when 3D printing technology is used [35].

Figure 9: 3D printing in Transdermal drug delivery system.

Clinical Trials:

The 3DP technology has been around for some time, but because it is expensive and not cost-effective, there are less successful implementations of this 3DP method in clinical centers and hospitals. Segmentation issues, as well as tough regulatory challenges, are also with the approach. There are currently few studies demonstrating the effectiveness of the 3DP strategy and the significant impact it may have on clinical decision-making and overall results. There are specialized and Randomized case-control research available, the majority which are released in the regions of gastroprotective floating pulsatile delivery systems, retinal vascular disease, and maxillofacial surgery and orthopaedics. Another area with a number of worthwhile research in the

interventional and educational domains is cardiology [36]. The technique makes it possible to use the product in incredibly tiny batch sizes with highly effective dosage variations for both preclinical research and first-in-human (FIH) studies; Additionally, because the pharmaceutical industry is under pressure to maximize R&D output or to accelerate the rate of commercialization out of the R&D pipelines, it helps to shorten the time period of drug development. Dosing flexibility provides a quick, effective, and accurate way to assess the dose and gather S&E data; products are purchased just before dosing for FIH trials, eliminating storage and shipping. stability testing, which eventually postpones the trials commencement [37]. A review of the clinical trial archive gives us information

regarding the upcoming 3D-printed goods or technology. Patents Like the internet and personal computers, 3DP is a disruptive technology, and adopting a disruptive technology is never without its challenges. The Widespread use and technical advancement truly took off in the late 2000s when reasonably priced, high-quality printers were first made generally accessible. To better safeguard manufacturers and customers, significant issues pertaining to 3D-printed medications, such as tort responsibility and property rights, must be resolved. Regulatory issues 3DP is unique among pharmaceutical technologies, and control measures pertaining to process parameters, RMSs, and manufacturing faults require particular attention. Unlike the demands in the case of the other products such as medical equipment, surgeries, training aids, and educational materials, the medication product faces an extremely tough regulatory demand placed on it. In contrast The primary benefit of using proven forms of administration and production procedures/tools is that research on excipient compatibility, drug release, etc. may be completed more quickly in the situation of creating goods without any after marketing statistics or clinical trial experience. In the future, hospital pharmacies and neighborhood pharmacies will play a fundamentally different function, and their inventory management strategies may alter, among other issues pertaining to safety and regulation. They may not have to keep an inventory of drugs (patent and generic) one of the issues critical to the issues of rules regarding the manufacture of drugs by 3D printer is the difference between formulated and manufactured

medicines. This question has huge effects on the 3D- printed products the extent of regulation. To share the early thoughts by the FDA on technical factors relating to additively manufactured devices, the USFDA released a guidance in 2017 titled "Technical Considerations for Additive Manufactured Devices." manufacture as well as praise for device testing and characterization. But as of right now, there are no set rules governing medicinal products that are 3D printed. There are a lot of unanswered concerns, including: will the 3D printer, "pharmaceutical ink," and Include the final output in the regulatory process? What regulatory path will the innovators pursue to get such unconventional products? To develop a comprehensive understanding of 3DP, the FDA carries out its own study^[38]. Two Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories (OSEL) labs are heading in the same direction: the FDA's Functional Efficiency and Device Use Laboratory and the Laboratory for Solid Materials. Additional guidelines for the approval of 3D-fabricated goods are provided by medical devices. More than 85 3D-printed implantable and therapeutic items have received FDA approval For FDA clearance, the most often utilized procedures include 510(k), PMA, de novo, HDE, and others. Due to the fact that "3D-printed products are significantly equivalent to a legally marketed device," all approved implants and medical devices created with this technology have so far been approved through the PMN process^[39]

The following is a regional distribution of clinical trial updates by product.

Figure10: Principal sites for 3DP clinical trials by nation.

Top 5 Companies Working On 3D Printing Projects:

1. AstraZeneca
2. GlaxoSmithKline
3. Pfizer
4. Merck
5. Johnson & Johnson^[40]

3D printing medications in hospital pharmacies is gaining attention as a viable option. It involves diagnosing patients and tailoring treatments based on individual characteristics. With existing

compounding facilities and trained staff, implementing 3D printing for personalized pharmaceuticals appears feasible. Recent studies show promising results; one trial involved treating children with maple syrup urine disease (MSUD) using 3D-printed chewable tablets and hand-filled capsules. The 3D-printed formulations were found to be more acceptable and accurate in dosing, suggesting improvements in quality and safety over traditional methods^[41].

Figure11: Demonstrates exemplary 3D-printed compositions that are suitable for use with pediatric patients.

Paediatrics has been transformed by 3D printing. Drug formulations, enabling the creation of appealing and customizable dosage forms for children. Innovations include chewable chocolate formulations containing ibuprofen and

paracetamol, printed with popular cartoon characters or geometric shapes to enhance engagement. Another development features soft, colorful, chewable candy made from gelatine and HPMC, making bitter medications more palatable.

Additionally, Lego™-shaped gelatine-based dosage forms have been created utilizing cutting-edge 3D printing methods. With an emphasis on a drop-on-powder technique for accurate dosage management, three-dimensional printing may also be used to generate other paediatric choices, such as small tablets and Oro-dispersible tablets. According to research, kids between the ages of 4 and 11 preferred these 3D-printed tablets' visual depiction over more conventional techniques, and they had consistent drug release patterns.^[42]

Future Potential:

One technology that turns digital data into tangible goods is the 3D printer. Even though it was initially established in the 1980s, it has grown astronomically in recent years. Similar to printing on 2D surfaces like paper in daily life, 3D printing has become extensively used in recent years due to the remarkable development in sales of 3DP equipment since the turn of the twenty-first century. Nowadays, everything may be printed, including jewellery, clothing, automobile parts, and even weapons. The innovation also shows up in the field of medicine, where it is starting to transform clinical choices and surgery. The following fields would greatly benefit from the technique. The field of regenerative medicine Manufacturing natural substances is now feasible because to developments in three-dimensional printing techniques before regenerative medicine, therefore not just a theory but reality of these possibilities^[43].

Short-term (2025-2030)

1. Personalized medicine: Tailored dosage forms, strengths, and release profiles.
2. Complex dosage forms: Multi-layer tablets, capsules, and implants.
3. Orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) and fast-dissolving films.
4. Implantable devices: Stents, implants, and scaffold-based tissue engineering.

5. Transdermal patches and microneedle-based drug delivery.

Mid-term (2030-2040)

1. Printed medications on demand.
2. Point-of-care manufacturing.
3. Customized pill boxes and packaging.
4. 3D-printed medical devices: Syringes, inhalers, and diagnostic tools.

Long-term (2040-2050)

1. Organ-on-a-chip technology for drug testing.
2. Bioprinting: Living tissue and organ printing.
3. Nanoscale 3D printing for targeted drug delivery.
4. Self-healing materials and shape-memory alloys.
5. Space-based pharmaceutical manufacturing^[44,45].

CONCLUSION:

3D printing is likely to have a major influence on the advancement of different ways to deliver drugs in the creation and production of pharmaceuticals. Applications for 3D printing in the health sector include pharmaceutical equipment, diagnostics, surgery, and medications. Given how quickly 3D printing technology is developing, Presumably, in the near future, it will be used to create customized organs for patients based on their anatomical requirements. Additionally, there are a number of unresolved issues, mostly related to regulatory viewpoints, that are thought to be resolved when various product categories have Recent technical developments and more research in the field will surely result in safer and more efficient treatments, as well as the possibility of individualized medicine The capacity of different 3D printing medication delivery techniques to offer distinct or personalized drug moiety release will surely enable tailored dose for individualized pharmaceutical therapy. As a novel tool for developing drug systems, stereolithography, linkjet printing, nozzle-based deposition systems, laser-based writing systems, and other common

3D printing processes used in drug manufacturing have attracted interest.

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